

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH)
Sent: Sun, 28 Oct 2018 14:53:46 +0000
To: Achrekar, Angeli
Cc: Williams, Yvonne (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (ljz0@cdc.gov)
Subject: Check-in

Hi Angeli –

It's been a month since we last spoke about the Alfred/SACTWU situation. Would you have time to check in for about 15 minutes this week?

Thanks –
Amy

Amy Herman-Roloff, PhD, MPH
Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext.9055
Cell: +27-82-524-0688
e-mail: bjy2@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

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From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 3 Sep 2018 11:38:35 +0000
To: Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD); Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Fwd: Dr Alfred Bere - media query for Dr Herman Roloff

Hi All -

First media query.

Working with Chantelle and PAS on a reply.

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

Begin forwarded message:

From: Marianne Thamm (b)(6)
Date: September 3, 2018 at 1:26:48 PM GMT+2
To: bjy2@cdc.gov
Subject: **Fwd: Dr Alfred Bere - media query for Dr Herman Roloff**

Sent from iCloud

Begin forwarded message:

From: Marianne Thamm (b)(6)
Date: September 03, 2018 1:20:26 PM
To: xyg8@cdc.gov
Subject: **Dr Alfred Bere - media query for Dr Herman Roloff**

Hi Chantelle...there is no address on your website for Dr Herman Roloff so I would appreciate that either you or she deal with the query with regard to the arrest and charging one Dr Bere.

Good afternoon Dr Herman-Roloff

As you may well be aware Dr. Alfred Bere, USDH CDC South Africa Prevention Branch Chief, appeared in the Cape Town Magistrate's court this morning on charges of fraud involving t least R25 million.

I am doing a story for the Daily Maverick with regard to Dr Bere's arrest and charging and brief appearance this morning.

It would be helpful if you, as Country Director, could reply/comment on the matter. Also was there any indication, prior to Dr Bere's arrest and detention, that there were matters amiss with regard to the massive amount that is stated in the Hawks charge sheet?

Also was their sufficient oversight on the part of the CDC with regard to Dr Bere's duties and functions as the SA Prevention Branch Chief.

I look forward to your reply. We are running the story tomorrow so a reply today would be in order.

Marianne Thamm

Assistant Editor
Daily Maverick

Sent from iCloud

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 18 Sep 2018 13:12:55 +0000
To: hallis2@state.gov
Subject: Fwd: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Lawyer info

Sent from my iPhone

Begin forwarded message:

From: "Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Date: September 17, 2018 at 8:02:31 PM GMT+2
To: "Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: (b)(6)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 7:54 PM
To: Alfred Bere (b)(6); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vfz3@cdc.gov>
Cc: rudi@bdk.co.za
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: Alfred Bere (b)(6)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 5:16 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); vfz3@cdc.gov
Cc: Ian Small-Smith; rudi@bdk.co.za
Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Regards,
Alfred

On Mon, Sep 17, 2018, 2:48 PM Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov> wrote:
Hello Alfred,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks,

Todd

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 15:20:55 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: FW: Items to address urgently

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

T

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:00 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Items to address urgently

Good morning Todd and Amy,

Feedback on the items below:

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Regards,

Martin Steyn, MCom
Associate Director for Operations
Insights® Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 12, 2018 9:05 PM
To: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vfz3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Items to address urgently

Hi Martin, per our call please:

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thx Todd

Todd Wilson, MS
Deputy Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9005
Cell: +27-82-524-4455
e-mail: twilson@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wed, 19 Sep 2018 09:01:25 +0000
To: Hall, Lydia S (Pretoria)
Subject: FW: Notification of Termination- A. Bere
Attachments: (b)(2), (b)(5); (b)(6)

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, September 18, 2018 11:10 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD) <rtm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjb7@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5); (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you both for your patience and support as this moved forward. I know this has been a trying time and I appreciate your engagement and rapid response to the swirl of inquiries that were required to generate this action. Please don't hesitate to reach out if you have any questions,

Ted

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 5 Oct 2018 11:22:06 +0000
To: Wray, Ivan A
Subject: FW: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Ivan –

For your awareness.

Best –
Amy

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, October 5, 2018 12:29 PM
To: McCary, Ian J (Pretoria) <McCaryIJ@state.gov>; Kraus, Jeffrey P (Pretoria) <KrausJP@state.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

For awareness:

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Please advise of any needed actions.

Best,

Todd

Todd Wilson, MS

Deputy Country Director
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Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9005
Cell: +27-82-524-4455
e-mail: twilson@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Sun, 11 Nov 2018 21:19:23 +0000
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Bicego, George (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: FW: Revised OIG 2019 PEPFAR Audit -- Capetown South Africa instead of Thailand
Attachments: Capetown SA Logistics_.xlsx
Importance: High

Hi All –

FYI – please see below.

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Please let me know if you have any questions.

Thanks –
Amy

From: DGHTPolicyRequest (CDC)
Sent: Friday, November 9, 2018 10:43 PM
To: Pape, Shelby L. (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <itb6@cdc.gov>; Naglich, Valerie (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <eoas5@cdc.gov>; Kun, Karen E. (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <icn3@cdc.gov>; Murray, Christi (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <cxm6@cdc.gov>; Hanson, Jeff (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <hbj6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Smith, Termika (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <KVL7@cdc.gov>; Williams, John K. (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <xka3@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Jordan, Regina (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <roj1@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>; Brown, J-Lynne (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <neu5@cdc.gov>
Subject: Revised OIG 2019 PEPFAR Audit -- Capetown South Africa instead of Thailand
Importance: High

This is a NEW audit for South Africa. This replacing Audit for Thailand.

More to come but this is a heads up.

John (J-Lyn)- please let Thailand know OIG will not be coming to Thailand in March. Country should notify Embassy as well as MoH. Please send

confirmation of Country's acknowledgement back to me at dghtpolicyrequest@cdc.gov .

I will notify South Africa Country office once a date has been confirmed and an official notification issued (which should contain the scope of work) . In the meantime, the attached spreadsheet includes an overview of logistics and the kind of assistance needed from CDC for scheduling meetings, transportation, documents etc. Please review to alert appropriate staff and give thought to the planning.

Valerie will be scheduling a conference call with country to discuss.

OIG!

Seh

From: Lomax, Janean (CDC/OD/OCS)
Sent: Friday, November 9, 2018 3:03 PM
To: DGHTPolicyRequest (CDC) <dghtpolicyrequest@cdc.gov>; Therrien, Jennifer January (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <jpz7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Naglich, Valerie (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT) <eoas5@cdc.gov>; Smith, Termika (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <KVL7@cdc.gov>; Israel, Stormie (CDC/OCOO/OFR/OPPC) <kwd1@cdc.gov>
Subject: Revised OIG 2019 PEPFAR Audit -- Capetown South Africa

Good afternoon –

HHS, OIG is getting ready to start their next country audit in January 2019. They previously mentioned Thailand but plans changed and now will audit recipient TB/HIV Care in Capetown South Africa. A start notice is expected soon which will include more details on the audit.

OIG is in the beginning stages of logistics and are still waiting on travel dates and cooperative agreement information. In the meantime, the attached spreadsheet includes an overview of logistics and the kind of assistance needed from CDC for scheduling meetings, transportation, documents etc. Please review to alert appropriate staff and give thought to the planning. I'll be in touch when more info is available.

Thanks,
Janean

Janean Lomax, DHEd
Audit Liaison | Office of the Chief of Staff
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
(404) 639-2809 (Office) | (404) 617-8456 (BB)

	Logistics	CDC Responses
1	Meet with Ambassador or official in Capetown South Africa for our brief-in/brief-out (waiting on travel dates)	
2	Schedule conference/phone meeting with CDC South Africa (SA) Country Director, Deputy Director, and TB/HIV Care Project Officer for our brief-in/brief-out (waiting on travel dates)	
3	We need assistance from CDC-SA with hotel in Capetown a. Issue is with full payment upfront/non refundable b. Heavy tourist season - most hotels are booked c. Looking at Marriott AC set open in December 2018 d. The other two hotes are Hilton and Radisson	
4	Assistance from CDC-SA with arranging safe transportation to/from audit site and hotel	
	Schedule appointment for vaccinations at CDC Roybal Clinic. We previously worked with Lee Ann Jean-Louis (LGJ4@cdc.gov).	Janean will coordiante
5	Will request documents from CDC ATL on recipient/award information (still waiting on CoAg information): 1. Official Award Files for recipient TB/HIV Care 2. Funding Opportunity Announcement (FOA) Binder as applicable to the time period 3. Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO) Binder as applicable to the time period (from Grants Solution) 4. The Pre FOA documentation 5. Audit Reports and MDLs (OGS/FAARU) 6.) OGAC Annual Progress Report for South Africa/TB HIV Care	
7	We need a CDC-SA point of contact to assist us with audit document request. The prior POC no longer works there. Or we go through CDC ATL for everything.	
8	We plan to submit an engagement letter to recipient to explain audit and request document request. We will need a recipient POC to provide instructions on how to submit documents through our secure delivery server (kiteworks). Or we go through CDC-SA or CDC ATL for everything. (still waiting on CoAg information and budget periods)	

From: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 4 Sep 2018 06:05:09 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: FW: SACTWU Media Holding Statement.docx
Attachments: SACTWU Media Holding Statement.docx

Hi Todd,

Statement as discussed - (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Look forward to your feedback.

Kind Regards,
Chantelle

From: Dave Clark <Dave.Clark@auruminstitute.org>
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 9:07 AM
To: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Helen Levin <hlevin@auruminstitute.org>; Dino Rech <DRRech@auruminstitute.org>; Jacqueline Pienaar <JPienaar@auruminstitute.org>
Subject: SACTWU Media Holding Statement.docx

Dear Chantelle

Please see the attached draft medical statement as discussed this morning. Please advise any changes you wish to see or whether its OK as is.

Kind regards
Dave

Dr Dave Clark

Regional Chief Executive Officer (RSA)

The Aurum Institute

Improving health in communities living
in poverty around the world.

Phone: +27 (0) 10 590 1303

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Website: www.auruminstitute.org

Department: Head Office Management

Division: Corporate Services

City/Town: Parktown Head Office

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(b)(5)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 25 Sep 2018 13:58:39 +0000
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: FW: SACTWU Work Health Program - Summary of CDC Support, Monitoring, and Findings
Attachments: SWHP Summary Final.docx

FYI

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Saturday, September 22, 2018 9:45 AM
To: 'Achrekar, Angeli' <AchrekarA@state.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: SACTWU Work Health Program - Summary of CDC Support, Monitoring, and Findings

Good morning Angeli –

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Attached please find a summary of CDC South Africa's support and monitoring of the SACTWU Worker's Health Program's (SWHP) VMMC activities.

Like you, CDC SA is fully committed to ensuring the accountability and impact of our PEPFAR-supported programs. We all had a concern that if the allegations (currently, not convictions) against Alfred are proven to be true, what impact may this have had on the program. As a result, CDC SA reviewed 12 years of our records to review all of our financial and program files on our support and oversight of the SWHP.

The attached 2-page document describes the outcomes of financial and program assessments that CDC SA conducted over the years. In summary, significant concerns regarding SWHP's financial and technical management of their program emerged in a 12-month period between mid-2016 and mid-2017. These were responded to appropriately via an external financial audit, enhanced monitoring, and significant training and development. Based on subsequent financial and program reviews of SWHP's VMMC program, it appears that these interventions mitigated poor performance.

We are continuing to explore opportunities to externally validate SWHP program data through triangulation with additional data sources (e.g., HSRC Household Survey, HIPPS Study data, etc.). If these additional analyses are performed, I will be sure to share them with you. Additionally, if Irum has any suggestions on how we can retrospectively review data 2015-2017 we would be grateful.

If you have any questions please let me know – I think that we should stay in close touch as the details of the investigation are revealed. Alfred's next court date is December 13.

Thank you for your support and ongoing collaboration.

With the highest regard,

Amy

Amy Herman-Roloff, PhD, MPH

Country Director

U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

Pretoria, South Africa

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Cell: +27-82-524-0888

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Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

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Oversight of the Southern African Clothing and Textile Workers' Union (SACTWU) Worker's Health Program

CDC South Africa (CDC SA) has had a long-standing working relationship with the SACTWU Worker's Health Program (SWHP); a registered non-governmental organization functionally independent from its parent union, SACTWU:

- Funding to SWHP began in 2006/2007, to provide comprehensive HIV prevention, care and treatment services. This funding, through a cooperative agreement with CDC, ended in 2012.
- In October 2011, SWHP received funding to provide voluntary medical male circumcision (VMMC) services as a prime partner under a cooperative agreement. Over the life of the cooperative agreement, SWHP received approximately \$40 million USD and lasted for five years, ending in December 2016.
- Subsequently, SWHP became a sub-partner under TB/HIV Care Association (THC) to offer VMMC services October 2016-September 2017, and then a sub-partner to Aurum Health beginning October 2017-September 2018. These sub-partnerships amounted to an additional \$13.5 million USD.
- There was a three-month period (October – December 2016) when SWHP was both a prime and sub-partner.

Through cooperative agreements, CDC collaborates with implementing partners to provide administrative, financial, and technical oversight. Numerous oversight visits were conducted by CDC SA staff to SWHP during their time as a prime partner. These visits included, but were not limited to, programmatic and financial reviews, visits to service delivery sites, and review of quality programming. None of these routine visits identified any adverse financial findings. Additionally, during this time, SWHP met most reporting and financial obligations including submission of annual progress reports and conducting annual audits required for all grantees. The submission of a final project report from this award remains outstanding.

In early 2016, CDC SA received a whistle blower complaint which alleged fraud and staffing irregularities at SWHP. A special review by CDC SA (in April 2016) found mismanagement of funds and improper hiring practices. As a result, SWHP reimbursed necessary funds to the U.S. Treasury and hiring practices were reviewed to ensure standards were being followed.

As a sub-partner to THC, several management and oversight concerns were raised regarding SWHP. As a result, and with CDC SA's approval, THC commissioned Marzars to conduct a financial forensic audit in mid-2017. This audit concluded that additional investigation was needed because SWHP did not comply with requirements of the audit, and, with CDC SA's approval, THC forwarded the investigation and materials to the HAWKS (the investigate directorate of the South African Police Services) and severed its relationship with SWHP. The HAWKS issued a search and seizure warrant to SHWP in October 2017 and the investigation is on-going.

Program Oversight of the SACTWU Worker's Health Program

To date, the SWHP has reported providing more VMMC services than any other implementing partner in South Africa, performing over 500,000 circumcisions, mostly in Kwa-Zulu Natal Province, but also in the Free State, Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga, North West, Northern Cape and Western Cape provinces:

- 392,636 VMMCs as a prime implementing partner between October 2011 and December 2016.
- 98,933 VMMCs as a sub-partner under THC between October 2016 and September 2017
- 40,942 VMMCs as a sub-partner under Aurum between October 2017 and present.

SWHP met or exceeded their targets for VMMC throughout their performance period, and CDC SA has monitored SWHP's programmatic performance, including oversight of services and monitoring and evaluation practices. For example, in 2012 and 2014, PEPFAR South Africa conducted external quality assurance

assessments of VMMC services in South Africa supported through CDC SA and USAID. During both of these assessments, no major quality issues were identified with SWHP's VMMC program. The SWHP sites that were visited during these assessments performed similar to the sites of other implementing partners, and findings indicated that the majority of quality standards were adequately met. Further, SWHP's "roving" model was identified as an innovative and promising practice that was encouraged to be expanded.

The most recent review of SWHP VMMC activities was conducted as part of a CDC-Atlanta technical review of CDC SA's entire VMMC program in August 2017. During this visit, for the first time on a significant scale, service quality irregularities were identified at SWHP sites, including 1) inadequate documentation and 2) prohibited use of forceps-guided method in clients aged <15 years. Following this visit, the CDC SA program initiated corrective actions with SWHP, including immediate training/re-training all SWHP circumcision providers on the dorsal slit (DS) method and a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) training for program staff in September 2017.

After THC ended its relationship with SWHP, CDC SA engaged Aurum to assume VMMC service delivery in Kwa-Zulu Natal Province, where the majority of the CDC SA VMMC program targets reside. With full knowledge of the program and financial oversight that would be required, Aurum planned to temporarily engage with SWHP for nine months to provide VMMC services in Kwa-Zulu Natal Province. This arrangement was temporary because CDC SA planned to identify new VMMC implementing partners in April 2018 through a competitive process.

When Aurum engaged SWHP as a sub-partner, they took precautionary measures to ensure rigorous financial and program oversight. Preparatory site assessments identified deficits in documentation, processes, and record keeping, and Aurum provided training and coaching in these areas which led to marked improvements. Additionally, Aurum arranged a payment-for-services contract with SWHP, rather than a conventional sub-partnership, which provided Aurum with added oversight and an opportunity to verify each VMMC service that SWHP reported as rendered. For example, during the initial period of collaboration, Aurum 'rejected' a high proportion of SWHP reported VMMCs (total rejected ~ 6,000), mostly due to insufficient or inadequate documentation. In the subsequent weeks the proportion of rejections rapidly decreased and remained low throughout the rest of the collaboration. During an unannounced audit in June, 2018, Aurum reported that SWHP's documentation and processes were satisfactory.

In recent months, Aurum/SWHP has been rapidly replaced by the new prime partners which have been awarded under CDC SA. In August 2018, SWHP reported only 836 VMMCs. In September 2018, that number is expected to decrease further as CDC SA ends its support of SWHP on September 30, 2018.

From: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
Sent: Wed, 12 Sep 2018 06:56:54 -0400
To: Sobush, Kathleen (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Shaba, Jane (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Chingwende, Rumbidzayi (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(5)
Attachments: (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Never a dull moment in the VMMC program!

Peter

Peter Vranken

Senior Program Officer
MassGenics Inc, assigned to:
Global AIDS Program - South Africa
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
PO box 9536, Brooklyn 0001
Pretoria, South Africa
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Tel. +27 12 4249000
Fax. +27 12 3464286
pbv7@cdc.gov

From: Miriam Mhazo <miriam@sfh.co.za>
Sent: Monday, August 20, 2018 5:01 PM
To: Bordelon, Keith (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <knb8@cdc.gov>
Cc: Bere, Alfred (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yek8@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Chingwende, Rumbidzayi (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <ojm4@cdc.gov>; Elizabeth Folsom <efolsom@psi.org>; Andrew Boner <aboner@psi.org>; Tasha Govender <tasha@sfh.co.za>; Shaba, Jane (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xec5@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(5)

Dear Mr. Bordelon

I hope this finds you well. Please find attached notification of suspected data fraud at two of our PSI/SFH sites. Once we have completed the investigations we will furnish you with the full report. Let me know if you have any questions.

Regards

SFH

Partners for
a healthier nation

Miriam Mhazo
Country Director
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Cel. +27 (0)82 820 3922
+27 (0)83 700 7395
Email. miriam@sfh.co.za
www.sfh.co.za

From: Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 9 Nov 2018 03:39:17 -0500
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH); Wilson, Todd (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH)
Subject: FW: TB HIV Care Prevention funding
Attachments: TB HIV Care GH001933-02 - Request for review of prevention funding decisions.pdf
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

(b)(5)

This email is an FYI to both you and Todd.

Regards

Rayna

Rayna Taback-Esra, MA
Senior Public Health Specialist
Office of the Director
Division of Global HIV/AIDS
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9016
Cell: +27-82-524-1119
e-mail: wvk7@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Harry Hausler <Hhausler@tbhivcare.org>
Sent: Friday, November 9, 2018 10:29 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wvk7@cdc.gov>; Gareth Lowndes <Gareth@tbhivcare.org>; Kuben Pillay <Kuben@tbhivcare.org>
Subject: FW: TB HIV Care Prevention funding
Importance: High

Dear Amy,

This is a gentle reminder to please indicate when it would be feasible to respond to the attached letter. Please confirm receipt.

We look forward to your visit next week.

Kind Regards,

Harry

Professor Harry Hausler
Chief Executive Officer

www.tbhivcare.org • Hhausler@tbhivcare.org

T: 021 425 0050 • **C:** 082 779 0045 • **F:** 021 421 9439
HO: 7th Floor • 11 Adderley Street • Cape Town • 8001 • South Africa
PO Box 2589 • Cape Town • 8001

Registered NPO 165-062

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From: Harry Hausler <Hhausler@tbhivcare.org>

Date: Monday, 22 October 2018 at 15:33

To: Amy Herman-Roloff <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Rayna Taback-Esra <wvk7@cdc.gov>

Subject: TB HIV Care Prevention funding

Dear Amy,

As discussed, TB HIV Care (THC) is concerned about the decrease in CDC funding from the Prevention Branch that has coincided with the audit and subsequent police investigation of SACTWU Worker Health Programme in which Alfred Bere was implicated and eventually arrested for potential fraud. We would be grateful if you would review our concerns and indicate when it would be feasible to respond. We would appreciate a response by 31 October 2018, if possible.

Kind Regards,

Harry

Harry Hausler
Chief Executive Officer

www.tbhivcare.org • Hhausler@tbhivcare.org

T: 021 425 0050 • **C:** 082 779 0045 • **F:** 021 421 9439
HO: 7th Floor • 11 Adderley Street • Cape Town • 8001 • South Africa
PO Box 2589 • Cape Town • 8001

Registered NPO 165-062

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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 12:21:42 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)
Attachments: image001.jpg

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

T

From: Alfred Ber (b)(6)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 5:16 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vfz3@cdc.gov>
Cc: ian@richmark.co.za; rudi@bdk.co.za
Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Regards,

(b)(2), (b)(5),
(b)(6)

On Mon, Sep 17, 2018, 2:48 PM Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov> wrote:
Hello Alfred,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks,

Todd

Todd Wilson, MS
Deputy Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9005
Cell: +27-82-524-4455
e-mail: twilson@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 4 Sep 2018 17:11:03 +0000
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

FYI –

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 3, 2018 3:23 PM
To: Collins, Matilda (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <vjq3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hig7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>; Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>; Edwards, Kamilia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fja3@cdc.gov>; Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <exu4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hello Matilda,

I hope you are having an enjoyable holiday weekend!

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you for your help,

Heather

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

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(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

XE Currency Converter: ZAR to USD

784,985 ZAR =
56,589.81 USD

South African Rand ↔ 1 USD = 13.8715
1 ZAR = US Dollar/ZAR
0.0720903 USD

Live mid-market rate 2016-11-29 17:38:16

ZAR to USD Chart

1 Dec 2015 05:00 UTC - 29 Nov 2016 17:34 UTC
ZAR/USD close **0.07209** low **0.05923** high **0.07555**

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XE Market Analysis

North American Edition

The dollar has ebbed back after making new trend highs during the European AM session. USD-JPY was showing a net 0.5% gain, as of the early European PM, although about half a big figure off from the seven-month high logged earlier at 113.53. EUR-USD ...

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XE Live Exchange Rates

	USD	EUR	GBP	INR	JPY
1.00000	0.94097	0.80025	68.5971	133.812	
1.06275	1.00000	0.85045	72.8950	142.000	
1.24961	1.17585	1.00000	85.7117	167.000	
0.01436	0.01372	0.01167	1.00000	0.01513	
0.74711	0.70108	0.59804	51.2500	100.000	

Marketplace Rates - 11/29/16 05:37

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 31 Aug 2018 10:02:04 -0400
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hello Heather -

I hope that you are well.

I am writing with the unfortunate news that the Front Office at U.S. Mission Pretoria made the decision that Dr. Alfred Bere may not resume his position with CDC South Africa.

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Best regards -

Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 30 Aug 2018 23:27:06 +0000
To: Franklin, Derrick L (OIG/OI) (Derrick.Franklin@oig.hhs.gov)
Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Humphrey, Shelia L. (CDC/OCOO/OD); Smagh, Kalwant (CDC/OCOO/OD)
Subject: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)
Attachments: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Hi Derrick,

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Thank you,

Heather

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: itmailbot@cdc.gov
Sent: Sat, 24 Nov 2018 11:33:57 -0500
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: ITSO GA SOUTH AFRICA - IT Incident Ticket: IM4655166 has been Opened

Ticket Escalation Notification

This is an Escalation Notification. Your Interaction is being escalated as follows:
ITSO ServiceDesk Ticket# **SD4449738** has been escalated to the appropriate support team.

The new ITSO ServiceDesk Ticket is ticket# **IM4655166**.

Once the escalated ticket is assigned to a technician, that technician will contact you.

To better assist you, please verify your contact information below.

Changes to this information can be made at <http://people.cdc.gov/>

DETAILS

Incident Number	IM4655166
Contact Name	Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
User ID	BJY2
Location	RFSS Bldg Rm /MS
Phone Number	012.424.9055
Description	<p>(POTENTIAL LEVEL III) - Hello -</p> <p>Alfred Bere is currently under investigation in South Africa as well as by the HHS OIG.</p> <p>Please preserve all data and information until further notice.</p> <p>Kindly confirm receipt of this email.</p> <p>Best regards - Amy</p> <p>[Amy Herman-Roloff-2]</p> <p>This e-mail is Official - SBU. This e-mail is UNCLASSIFIED.</p> <p>From: MISOCDCIS (CDC)</p>

Sent: Friday, November 23, 2018 11:52 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: People Processing: Alfred Bere has been deactivated

This email has been automatically generated by People Processing. Please do not respond to this email.

The person profile for Alfred Bere (YEK8) has been deactivated.

All CDC computer accounts will be closed for this person. If this user's email account is under a litigation hold or otherwise contains federal records requiring preservation, the supervisor should contact the ITSO Service Desk at (404) 639-6000 or ITSOservicedesk@cdc.gov to request preservation of the data within 15 days of this notice.

If this person were to return to CDC, please note that this profile may be reactivated. You would not need to create a new profile.

If you have questions or concerns about this action, please contact the MISO HelpDesk at magichelp@cdc.gov or 404-639-7500.

11/24/18 11:32:56 (LWE3):

Checked customer contact information and all is correct.

11/24/18 11:32:56 (LWE3):

Checked for existence of duplicate calls/incident, unresolved calls/incidents, and open calls/incidents with the following discovery:

nr

For helpful tips and other information please visit the ITSO intranet page located at <http://intranet.cdc.gov/ocio/>.

To check your ticket status, please visit the ITSO Service Desk portal at

<http://itsoservicedesk.cdc.gov> and click on View Open Tickets.

Please DO NOT reply to this email, it is from an automated mailbox. Contact your helpdesk and refer to ticket number [IM4655166](#) if you need further assistance.

From: ITSOSQL1 (CDC)
Sent: Fri, 23 Nov 2018 23:55:41 -0500
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/DDPHSIS/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: ITSO Out-Processing - Bere, Alfred - Request Initiated - effective 11/23/2018
11:55:02 PM

According to CDC People Processing, **Bere, Alfred** is no longer cleared for CDC network access effective **11/23/2018 11:55:02 PM** and their network account has been automatically disabled. Your assistance is needed as the listed Manager to ensure IT resources assigned to this employee are properly reclaimed or dispositioned in a timely manner.

Action needed as soon as possible, if not already completed.

1. Acquire all devices listed on the Device Report below. This list includes desktops, laptops, and keyfobs. This equipment should typically be turned over to ITSO for reuse, unless it was purchased using your program funds and you wish to retain it.
2. Acquire all government-owned mobile devices including BlackBerries, Apple iOS and Android devices the departed employee may have associated with them, and return them to your iSYS/WidePoint Point of Contact. If all government-owned mobile devices are not acquired, ensure they have been deactivated. (Note: Not all Mobile Devices will be listed in the device report. Please refer to your iSYS/WidePoint Point of Contact for a complete list of mobile devices and to confirm government-owned devices.)
3. Acquire all government-owned teleworking equipment the departed employee may have had in their possession, including non-barcoded peripherals such as printers, docking stations, displays, etc. This equipment should typically be turned over to ITSO for reuse, unless it was purchased using your program funds and you wish to retain it.
4. Review and remove any 'local' application's access, Outlook delegate permissions, or specific SharePoint permissions for the departed employee. If the departed employee was the owner of any listserv, assign another owner and remove the departed employee.

Automated ITSO actions beginning on 11/27/2018 11:55:41 PM:

1. The employee's mobile device is wiped of any CDC data.

Automated ITSO actions beginning on 12/7/2018 11:55:41 PM:

1. The employee's My Documents, My Archive and My Large Workspace data will be moved to a location with Read-Only access for you as the Manager to process. You will have 90 days to review and take action to preserve important data before it is deleted. You will receive reminders at 30 and 60 days.

2. Multi-User Share Tool (MUST) notifications will be sent to the data stewards informing them the departing employee was removed from the specified multi-user shares.
3. Distribution List Management Tool (DLMT) notifications will be sent to the DL managers informing them the departing employee was removed from the specified DLs.
4. The employee's Skype account and voicemail boxes will be removed.
5. All keyfobs assigned to the employee will be deactivated.
6. A Service Manager ticket will be automatically opened for an ITSO technician to work with the Manager to collect computer peripherals that may be left after the employee departs.
7. The employee's RightFax account will be removed.
8. Access to Service Manager and any associated groups will be removed.
9. Any data on the Consolidated Statistical Platform (CSP) will be reviewed and the employee's access removed.
10. Access through the Website Administration Tool (WSAT) and Web Services Request Tool (WSRT) will be removed for the departing employee.

Request IOP Suspension

If you would like to suspend the IOP actions listed in this message, please go to the [ITSOTools IOP](#) page to request a suspension of activities.

Device Report

Name	Description	Barcode	Category
DELL E7250	COMPUTER LAPTOP	0000234552	Hardware Devices
RSA	RSA Keyfob	156191578	Keyfobs
iOS iPhone	LAST_ACTIVITY: 5/31/2018	FFMQF2PGG5MR	GOE Mobile Device
iOS iPhone	LAST_ACTIVITY: 8/26/2018	F4GVT8ZYJC67	GOE Mobile Device

More information on the automated ITSO out-processing can be found on the [ITSO Equipment Out-Processing](#) web page.

This message is from an automated system. Do not respond to this address. If you have any questions please contact the ITSO Service Desk.

ITSO Service Desk
 itsoservicedesk@cdc.gov
 http://ITSOServiceDesk.cdc.gov
 (404) 639-6000
 1-888-647-3375

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 11 Sep 2018 04:55:04 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Management Meeting Notes - 9/11

Good morning,

Please find the notes from this morning's management meeting below:

- City of Tshwane issued a notice to citizens to conserve water. Water levels are lower than expected.
- Newcomers briefing tomorrow, September 12 at the Chancery.
- High School student briefing on Sunday, September 16 – RSO/Med/POSHO will provide briefings.
- Medical Unit reception with Management Officer on 28th
- Welcome to Post party on the 30th (please RSVP)
- Heritage Day celebrations on October 3rd from 14:00 – 17:00. Contributions/Entertainment wanted.
- FMO end of year braai on October 5th
- GSO end of year braai on October 12th
- Paul and Sandra will be out of the office from November 5th to 9th for a HR/OE Conference.
- Alfred Bere case was briefly mentioned – Alfred is still being detained (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

- Received vague threats for 9/11. Additional police presence will be noticeable.
- There will be a protest at the Embassy on Friday following the "Trump tweet". Will try and keep it low-key even though certain outside parties are trying to blow this story up.
- Blood Drive – November 1st. A few people requested advanced notice. Will send out notifications for the next one.
- End of year deadlines:
 - Procurement deadline passed
 - Travel processing deadline is September 20th
 - Payment deadline is September 21st
- There are a lot of cash advances outstanding from traveling staff. No travel authorizations will be approved without outstanding advances being fully paid up.
- FMO will become stricter on processing times – late requests will not be processed (this was a discussion I had with Brian Skinner after the meeting).

Regards,

Martin Steyn, MCom

Associate Director for Operations
Insights@ Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa

Tel: +27-12-424-9000

Cell: +27-82-524-4792

E-mail: vfz3@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica>

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From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wed, 12 Sep 2018 13:10:02 +0000
To: Marianne Thamm
Subject: Re: Alfred Bere

Hello Marianne -

Please send any inquiries to the U.S. Embassy's Acting Spokesperson, Caroline Schneider.

Best regards -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

> On Sep 12, 2018, at 1:30 PM, Marianne Thamm <mariannethamm@icloud.com> wrote:

>

> Hi Amy

> You might be aware Alfred Bere was granted R100 000 bail in the magistrate's court today with very strict conditions for the charges of Fraud and Corruption amounting to R25 million. I have a question for you with regard to whether Mr Bere was asked by yourself, as the Country Director, to not leave South Africa after complaints had been received by the CDC?

> I look forward to your reply

> Regards

> Marianne Thamm

> Daily Maverick

>

>

>

>

>

> Sent from iCloud

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 14:33:48 -0400
To: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Alfred Update

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

T

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:28 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Alfred Update

Good morning,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Kind regards,

Martin Steyn, MCom

Associate Director for Operations
Insights@ Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000
Cell: +27-82-524-4792
E-mail: vfz3@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica>

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To: Achrekar, Angeli <AchrekarA@state.gov>
Subject: Alfred

Hi Angeli –

Hope you are well!

I'm sure you are swamped, but I wanted to connect with you about Alfred.

(b)(5)

(b)(5) The article wasn't entirely correct, so here are the facts:

- Alfred was arrested on August 25, 2018 in Musina.
- The arrest warrant lists the charges as "Fraud and Corruption", and activities related to the charges were estimated to have taken place in 2016.

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

- We've provided guidance to PEPFAR staff and partners to direct media enquiries to Chantelle (CDC Director of Comms). Chantelle then loops in PAS.
- Alfred's first court appearance was yesterday – very short, and mainly to set the next hearing date (Sept 12).

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 20 Sep 2018 10:20:38 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(5)

Martin Steyn, MCom
Associate Director for Operations
Insights@ Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000
Cell: +27-82-524-4792
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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 20, 2018 4:16 PM
To: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vfz3@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

T

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 20, 2018 4:14 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Good afternoon Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Regards,

Martin Steyn, MCom

Associate Director for Operations
Insights@ Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000
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E-mail: vfz3@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica>

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From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wed, 12 Sep 2018 19:47:34 -0400
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(6)

Thanks Heather!

Sent from my phone.

> On Sep 12, 2018, at 7:46 PM, Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov> wrote:

> (b)(2), (b)(6)

> Sent from my iPhone

>> On Sep 12, 2018, at 7:41 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

>> (b)(6), (b)(2)

>> Thanks, Ted

>>

>> Sent from my phone.

<tiw6@cdc.gov>

Cc: Vinter, Serena (CDC/CGH/OD) <uvv3@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>; Hansen, Donda L. (CDC/CGH/OD) <xcb1@cdc.gov>; Dougherty, Pamela (CDC/CGH/OD) <phd4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Draft media responses re: CDC case

Dear Chantelle and Todd,

Thank you. [REDACTED (b)(5)]

I will try to arrange a call between OADC, OFR, you and us for early morning as soon as possible.

While I am waiting for it to become daylight here, can I have a brief call with either of you now to review specific messaging you would like FO to convey?

Chantelle – I see your light is green. I will try calling you now.

Thank you,

Laura

From: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:25 AM

To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD) <wpg3@cdc.gov>

Cc: Vinter, Serena (CDC/CGH/OD) <uvv3@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>; Hansen, Donda L. (CDC/CGH/OD) <xcb1@cdc.gov>; Dougherty, Pamela (CDC/CGH/OD) <phd4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Draft media responses re: CDC case

Morning,

Currently four articles (all South African based press) relating – will continue to monitor.

<https://www.dailymaverick.co.za/article/2018-09-13-r100000-bail-for-sa-branch-chief-at-us-centre-for-disease-control-arrested-on-r25m-corruption-and-fraud-charges/>

<https://www.timeslive.co.za/news/south-africa/2018-09-12-american-alfred-bere-in-court-over-allegations-of-using-ngo-money-for-personal-gain/>

<https://www.news24.com/SouthAfrica/News/fraud-accused-centre-for-disease-control-boss-released-on-r100k-bail-20180912>

<https://www.iol.co.za/capetimes/news/virologist-granted-r100-000-bail-in-fraud-trial-17042000>

In all, besides the Daily Maverick, we were not approached for comment.

Our window to influence the messaging that FO will eventually give is rapidly closing.

Kind Regards,

Chantelle

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:51 AM
To: Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD) <wpg3@cdc.gov>; Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>
Cc: Vinter, Serena (CDC/CGH/OD) <uvv3@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>; Hansen, Donda L. (CDC/CGH/OD) <xcb1@cdc.gov>; Dougherty, Pamela (CDC/CGH/OD) <phd4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Draft media responses re: CDC case

Hi Laura,

Alfred has made bail today and is now back in Pretoria. The reporter from the Maverick sent a list of questions to the embassy press officer yesterday. [REDACTED]

(b)(5)

[REDACTED] I am sure more will develop today. I have posted the questions below.

On Sep 12, 2018, at 5:13 PM, Schneider, Caroline M <SchneiderCM@state.gov> wrote:

Marianne Thamm from Daily Maverick sent the questions below. I don't know the latest on his whereabouts or next steps, and I don't want to selectively answers some questions and avoid others, so unless there are objections, I'm inclined to stick with this very unsatisfying response: ***"As previously noted, we are working closely with South African officials and cannot comment further on an ongoing investigation."***

I was tempted to at least answer the highlighted question, but I feel like even repeating the word "fraud" subtly implies some guilt.

From: Marianne Thamm [REDACTED]
Sent: Wednesday, September 12, 2018 4:03 PM
To: Schneider, Caroline M
Subject: Dr Alfred Bere - questions

Hi Caroline - As you might be aware Dr Bere was released on R100 000 bail today. He is facing charges of corruption and fraud. In this regard I have a few questions that I hope you would be able to answer. This is a hugely serious matter as you no doubt are aware. Below are my questions. Hopefully you will be able to respond. My report on Dr Bere's appearance and his statement made in support of his bail application will be part of the story.

- How did Dr Alfred Bere maintain a security clearance to work for the US mission after numerous reports of fraud/corruption/conflict of interest?
- Is Dr Bere currently part of US mission to SA?
- Is he living in Embassy housing?
- Has his clearance been revoked since his arrest and charge?

- If Dr Bere was driving to Zimbabwe on vacation when he was apprehended on 24/8, was he scheduled to work on Monday?
- Are USDHs required to notify the US embassy when leaving the country?
- Is Dr Bere the current prevention branch chief at CDC-SA?
- Is he a US direct hire as indicated in Dr Amy Herman Rolof's mail to partners, or is he a TCN DH (third country national direct hire)?
- At what point was the embassy made aware of allegations of corruption against Dr Bere?
- What type of investigation was conducted by the RSO (regional security officer) following these allegations of corruption?
- Is Dr Bere still residing in Embassy housing?
- If still employed by CDC, will Dr Bere be able to write RFAs? Oversee partners? Supervise CDC staff or make funding decisions or inputs on funding decisions?
- Are any internal investigations being conducted?
- When did Gbolahan Cole leave mission South Africa?
- The number Dr Bere provided to the court (082 524 3334) was his US government cell phone. Does he still have a US government issued work phone?
- **Is the Embassy concerned with preventing fraud of US government funds?**
- Is the embassy currently following up on any of the numerous allegations of corruption/fraud involving Dr Bere or the CDC MMC program in general?

I look forward to your reply

Regards

Marianne Thamm

Assistant Editor

Daily Maverick

From: Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD)

Sent: Wednesday, September 12, 2018 10:46 PM

To: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Cc: Vinter, Serena (CDC/CGH/OD) <uvv3@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>; Hansen, Donda L. (CDC/CGH/OD) <xcb1@cdc.gov>; Dougherty, Pamela (CDC/CGH/OD) <phd4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Draft media responses re: CDC case

Dear Todd and Chantelle,

Checking on any updates. I am awaiting cleared talking points from OADC. I located the Daily Maverick article from 9 days ago.

Will send you talking points as soon as they are cleared.

Am available here and by phone via Skype or at +1 404 702 9763.

From: Berger, Sherri (CDC/OCOO/OD)
Sent: Wed, 12 Sep 2018 22:06:35 -0400
To: Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD)
Cc: Daniel, Katherine Lyon (CDC/OD/OADC); Harben, Kathy (CDC/OD/OADC);
Patterson, John (CDC/OCOO/OD); Bonds, Michelle E. (CDC/OD/OADC); Kelly, Bertram (CDC/OD/OADC);
Smagh, Kalwant (CDC/OCOO/OD)
Subject: Follow up from our call
Attachments: Questions_revised_cm_V3_9 12 18_10am_KH_CLEAN (002).docx

Hi Laura –

(b)(5)

We are happy to speak with the country office tomorrow, if helpful.

Thanks,
Sherri

From: Berger, Sherri (CDC/OCOO/OD)
Sent: Wed, 12 Sep 2018 22:27:24 -0400
To: Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD)
Cc: Daniel, Katherine Lyon (CDC/OD/OADC); Harben, Kathy (CDC/OD/OADC); Patterson, John (CDC/OCOO/OD); Bonds, Michelle E. (CDC/OD/OADC); Kelly, Bertram (CDC/OD/OADC); Smagh, Kalwant (CDC/OCOO/OD); Hansen, Donda L. (CDC/CGH/OD)
Subject: RE: Follow up from our call

Thanks Laura. John Patterson will assist you with OCOO information and OADC with handle overall clearance of the document before it can be released. Have a good night

From: Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD) <wpg3@cdc.gov>
Date: September 12, 2018 at 10:25:20 PM EDT
To: Berger, Sherri (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sob8@cdc.gov>
Cc: Daniel, Katherine Lyon (CDC/OD/OADC) <kdl8@cdc.gov>, Harben, Kathy (CDC/OD/OADC) <kxh9@cdc.gov>, Patterson, John (CDC/OCOO/OD) <byi8@cdc.gov>, Bonds, Michelle E. (CDC/OD/OADC) <meb0@cdc.gov>, Kelly, Bertram (CDC/OD/OADC) <msy5@cdc.gov>, Smagh, Kalwant (CDC/OCOO/OD) <wpg5@cdc.gov>, Hansen, Donda L. (CDC/CGH/OD) <xcb1@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Follow up from our call

Dear Sherri and All,

Thank you for your input. I am making the suggested changes and sending to SA country office.

If you could, let me know if OFR, OGS and HRO are able to clear tomorrow the sections you identified for them.

Will keep you abreast of any updates.

Thanks again for your feedback,

Laura

From: Berger, Sherri (CDC/OCOO/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, September 12, 2018 10:07 PM
To: Bellinger, Laura (CDC/CGH/OD) <wpg3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Daniel, Katherine Lyon (CDC/OD/OADC) <kdl8@cdc.gov>; Harben, Kathy (CDC/OD/OADC) <kxh9@cdc.gov>; Patterson, John (CDC/OCOO/OD) <byi8@cdc.gov>; Bonds, Michelle E. (CDC/OD/OADC) <meb0@cdc.gov>; Kelly, Bertram (CDC/OD/OADC) <msy5@cdc.gov>; Smagh, Kalwant (CDC/OCOO/OD) <wpg5@cdc.gov>
Subject: Follow up from our call

Hi Laura –

(b)(5)

We are happy to speak with the country office tomorrow, if helpful.

Thanks,
Sherri

From: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 4 Sep 2018 11:53:44 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Yeah

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 11:14 AM
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: First story re Alfred Bere printed

FYI ☺

(b)(6)

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 5:12 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Fwd: First story re Alfred Bere printed

FYI. (b)(6). Completely unrelated to Alfred.

Sent from my iPhone

Begin forwarded message:

From: "Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <hjk7@cdc.gov>
Date: September 4, 2018 at 11:04:25 AM EDT
To: "Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Last minute request Thurs/Friday from CGH for Voice of America to interview me, Rebecca, and Sarita about TB.

Sarita can't make it (b)(6)

Hank Tomlinson, Ph.D.
Director, Division of Global HIV & TB
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
[404-639-8307](tel:404-639-8307) (office)
*sent via mobile device

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>

Date: September 4, 2018 at 10:43:30 AM EDT
To: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>
Subject: Fwd: First story re Alfred Bere printed

I think I missed something. Are you being interviewed or making a statement or what?

Sent from my iPhone

Begin forwarded message:

From: "Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD)" <isc4@cdc.gov>
Date: September 4, 2018 at 10:31:33 AM EDT
To: "Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <hjg7@cdc.gov>, "Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <bjy2@cdc.gov>, "Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <hbp7@cdc.gov>, "Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)" <fpp0@cdc.gov>, "Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <gp4@cdc.gov>, "Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: "Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <xyg8@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Dear Hank,

Your call time today will be 2PM. Please come to the Roybal campus and go to the makeup suite. I will meet you there at 2PM. We will be recording in studio B today and will start your interview around 2:30 PM.

Do you have time to speak with me briefly before noon today?

Many thanks,

Amy

From: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 4:52 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gp4@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>
Cc: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Thanks, Amy.

Hank Tomlinson, Ph.D.
Director, Division of Global HIV & TB

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
[404-639-8307](tel:404-639-8307) (office)
*sent via mobile device

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Date: September 4, 2018 at 2:08:35 AM EDT
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>, Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>, Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>, Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>, Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>
Cc: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>
Subject: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Hi All -

For your awareness - following is the first story that has been printed about Alfred's arrest and detainment:

<https://www.dailymaverick.co.za/article/2018-09-03-cdc-chief-south-africa-court-alfred-bere/>

Chantelle does an excellent job monitoring the media and will keep us informed if this gets any traction.

Best -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tue, 4 Sep 2018 15:07:25 +0000
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: First story re Alfred Bere printed

No idea.

(b)(5)

If you hear anything – please let me know.

From: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 4:36 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Hi Amy, do you know what this is about

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Best Regards, George

From: Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 10:32 AM
To: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Dear Hank,

Your call time today will be 2PM. Please come to the Roybal campus and go to the makeup suite. I will meet you there at 2PM. We will be recording in studio B today and will start your interview around 2:30 PM.

Do you have time to speak with me briefly before noon today?

Many thanks,

Amy

From: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 4:52 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

<gpb4@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>

Cc: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>

Subject: Re: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Thanks, Amy.

Hank Tomlinson, Ph.D.

Director, Division of Global HIV & TB
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

[404-639-8307](tel:404-639-8307) (office)

*sent via mobile device

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Date: September 4, 2018 at 2:08:35 AM EDT

To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>, Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>, Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>, Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>, Rowland, Amy (CDC/CGH/OD) <isc4@cdc.gov>

Cc: Van Schalkwyk, Chantelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <xyg8@cdc.gov>

Subject: First story re Alfred Bere printed

Hi All -

For your awareness - following is the first story that has been printed about Alfred's arrest and detainment:

<https://www.dailymaverick.co.za/article/2018-09-03-cdc-chief-south-africa-court-alfred-bere/>

Chantelle does an excellent job monitoring the media and will keep us informed if this gets any traction.

Best -

Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Sat, 15 Sep 2018 23:39:14 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: follow-up with Alfred

Hi Amy –

1. (b)(2); (b)(5)
- 2.
- 3.

T

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Saturday, September 15, 2018 10:51 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: follow-up with Alfred

Hi Heather and Todd –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks all!

Amy

Amy Herman-Roloff, PhD, MPH

Country Director

U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

Pretoria, South Africa

Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext.9055

Cell: +27-82-524-0888

e-mail: bjv2@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

This e-mail is **Official - SBU**. This e-mail is **UNCLASSIFIED**.

From: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 11:23:59 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR); Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Fresh Eyes to Review
Attachments: SWHP Summary v2 091518_jzh_ct.docx

All,

Attached are my initial comments (together with Jonas').

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Happy to have a call to talk through it if needed. Just let me know.

C

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 10:12 AM
To: Toledo, Carlos (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <cot8@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Fresh Eyes to Review

Just some docs I have on hand. Some may be useful, some not.

T

(b)(5)

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wed, 3 Oct 2018 02:44:12 -0400
To: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD)
Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: HHE for Alfred Bere

Thanks Sandra, I will sort the issues and logistics here then come back to you with the proposed plan.

T

From: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 4:36 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: HHE for Alfred Bere

Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

If you think it might be useful to have a call to further discuss, let me know. I can try to schedule a call sometime this week with Eva Holland in OGC.

Thanks

From: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 8:46 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: HHE for Alfred Bere

I have a call into OGC now.

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 8:37 AM
To: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>

Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: HHE for Alfred Bere

Thanks, (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks

T

From: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD)

Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 2:27 PM

To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: HHE for Alfred Bere

Todd,

Jessie is out, but the usual procedure apply. If for some reason Alfred is not available to pack up his HHE, a representative can be appointed by him (or for him) to pack up on his behalf.

Once you let me know you are ready to proceed, I will complete a relocation request. Once submitted to FS, they will reach out either to Alfred or to his representative.

Please advise.

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Monday, October 1, 2018 7:26 AM

To: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>

Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>;

Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Subject: HHE for Alfred Bere

Spoke with Alfred. He wants to ship

(b)(6)

(b)(6)

(b)(5)

If you could give me some ideas about process and timeline I will discuss with Management and GSO at the embassy.

Thanks!

T

Thanks

From: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 8:46 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: HHE for Afred Bere

I have a call into OGC now.

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 8:37 AM
To: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: HHE for Afred Bere

Thanks. I will discuss with the embassy.

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks

T

From: Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 2:27 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Aukes, Jessie (CDC/CGH/OD) <jxp6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: HHE for Afred Bere

Todd,

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 15:59:42 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Ent1@cdc.gov

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 9:58 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Items to address urgently

I'm only on my phone today - any chance you have Nathan's email?

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 9:20 PM, Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi, I think we need (b)(5)

(b)(5)

T

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:00 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Items to address urgently

Good morning Todd and Amy,

Feedback on the items below:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Regards,

<image001.png>

This e-mail is **SBU** and may contain **PII**. This e-mail is **UNCLASSIFIED**.

The information contained in this e-mail is intended only for the individual/s named. If you are not the named addressee you should not disseminate, distribute or copy this e-mail. Please notify the sender immediately by e-mail if you have received this e-mail by mistake and delete this e-mail from your system. E-mail transmission cannot be guaranteed to be secure or error-free as information could be intercepted, corrupted, lost, destroyed, arrive late or incomplete, or contain viruses. The sender therefore does not accept liability for any errors or omissions in the contents of this message, which arise as a result of e-mail transmission.

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 12, 2018 9:05 PM
To: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vfz3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Items to address urgently

Hi Martin, per our call please:

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thx Todd

<image002.jpg>

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 11:57:26 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy,

(b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:55 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thanks Heather – a timeline would be very helpful.

(b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:50 PM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Eva (b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thank you.

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:35 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Eva

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:33 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:29 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thank you!

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:23 AM

To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hello –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:19 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy,

Thanks so much for the detailed outline of events!

Just to confirm:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Take care,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:12 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)

<fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

Thank you for your email and giving me the opportunity to correct the information in the email below.

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:39 PM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Meeting with RSO
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

Could you please verify the following:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

*Eva M. Holland
Senior Attorney
HHS Office of the General Counsel
Public Health Division
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., MS D-53
Atlanta, GA 30333
(404) 639-7445 (phone)
(404) 639-7351 (fax)*

This e-mail message is intended for the exclusive use of the recipient(s) named above. It may contain information that is protected, privileged, or confidential, and it should not be disseminated, distributed, or copied to persons not authorized to receive such information. If you are not the intended recipient, any dissemination, distribution, or copying is strictly prohibited. If you think you have received this e-mail message in error, please notify the sender immediately.

From: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 14 Sep 2018 14:37:32 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Have a enjoyable weekend with family!

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:37 PM
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

Thanks George -
Hoping Chris and his team can help to move this forward from here.

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 11:34 PM, Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov> wrote:

Thank you for the critical role you are playing. cheers

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:10 PM
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

Yes -
Got out on bail yesterday
Then DIRCO denied immunity today
His trial starts Dec 13
Lots of media coverage today

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 11:08 PM, Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov> wrote:

I thought he was getting out on bail though, no?

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:01 PM
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>
Subject: Fwd: Meeting with RSO

FYI...

It's been a doozy of a day re Alfred. (Plus a POART!)

DIRCO replied and denied immunity.

Sent from my iPhone

Begin forwarded message:

From: "Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <csp2@cdc.gov>
Date: September 13, 2018 at 9:15:19 PM GMT+2
To: "Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Cc: "Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)" <fpp0@cdc.gov>, "Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <bjy2@cdc.gov>, "Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Good afternoon and happy Thursday.

Good deal. Will do.

Thx

Chris

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 3:14 PM
To: Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: Meeting with RSO

Hi Chris, (b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(5); (b)(2)

(b)(5); (b)(2)

I saw your note earlier that

(b)(6)

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Thank you. - Heather

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 3:02 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 2:02 PM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Eva- (b)(5); (b)(2)

(b)(5); (b)(2)

Thanks, Ted

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 1:00 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Ted,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:58 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

I will ask Keith Eichenholz.

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:50 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Eva (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thank you.

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:35 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Eva

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:33 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:29 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thank you!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:23 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hello –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:19 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy,

Thanks so much for the detailed outline of events!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Take care,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:12 AM

To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:39 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Meeting with RSO
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

*Eva M. Holland
Senior Attorney
HHS Office of the General Counsel
Public Health Division
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., MS D-53
Atlanta, GA 30333
(404) 639-7445 (phone)
(404) 639-7351 (fax)*

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From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Sat, 15 Sep 2018 07:08:16 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

Thanks Amy- we have 20 T42 staff internationally a (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Sound like a tentative plan? Happy to hear Heather's thoughts too. Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 15, 2018, at 2:19 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Heather and Ted –

(b)(5)

There are many more ☺ but just to give you a flavor.

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 6:58 PM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2); (b)(5)

Hi,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Please let me know if you need anything!

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 3:07 PM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thanks, Amy!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Enjoy your evening,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 2:09 PM

To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

Hi All -

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 8:02 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

Eva- (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks, Ted

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 1:00 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Ted,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:58 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

I will ask Keith Eichenholz.

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:50 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Eva – (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thank you.

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:35 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Eva

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Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:33 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:29 AM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thank you!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

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To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hello –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –

Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
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Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy,

Thanks so much for the detailed outline of events!

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Take care,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:12 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:39 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Meeting with RSO
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

*Eva M. Holland
Senior Attorney
HHS Office of the General Counsel
Public Health Division
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., MS D-53
Atlanta, GA 30333
(404) 639-7445 (phone)
(404) 639-7351 (fax)*

This e-mail message is intended for the exclusive use of the recipient(s) named above. It may contain information that is protected, privileged, or confidential, and it should not be disseminated, distributed, or copied to persons not authorized to receive such information. If you are not the intended recipient, any dissemination, distribution, or copying is strictly prohibited. If you think you have received this e-mail message in error, please notify the sender immediately.

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Sat, 15 Sep 2018 05:51:19 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: "Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Sent: Saturday, 15 September 2018 08:14
To: "Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)" <btq9@cdc.gov>,"Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <hbp7@cdc.gov>,"Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)" <fpp0@cdc.gov>
CC: "Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

Thanks for the update.

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 6:58 PM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Please let me know if you need anything!

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 3:07 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thanks, Amy!

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Enjoy your evening,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 2:09 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

Hi All -

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 8:02 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks, Ted

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 1:00 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Ted,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:58 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>;

Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

I will ask Keith Eichenholz.

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:50 AM

To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Eva – (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thank you.

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:35 AM

To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Eva

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:33 AM

To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Can we please streamline the requests to the RSO? (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:29 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thank you!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:23 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hello –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:19 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy,

Thanks so much for the detailed outline of events!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Take care,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:12 AM

To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCCO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:39 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Meeting with RSO
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

*Eva M. Holland
Senior Attorney*

*HHS Office of the General Counsel
Public Health Division
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., MS D-53
Atlanta, GA 30333
(404) 639-7445 (phone)
(404) 639-7351 (fax)*

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From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 12:25:25 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thank you. Very helpful.

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 12:14 PM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

Thanks again for asking for clarity.

I've replied item by item below.

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:55 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy and Todd,

(b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:12 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:39 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Meeting with RSO
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

*Eva M. Holland
Senior Attorney
HHS Office of the General Counsel
Public Health Division
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., MS D-53
Atlanta, GA 30333
(404) 639-7445 (phone)
(404) 639-7351 (fax)*

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prohibited. If you think you have received this e-mail message in error, please notify the sender immediately.

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Sun, 16 Sep 2018 13:48:59 +0000
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Happy to talk this through more over the phone.

I don't think that you owe me anything:)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 16, 2018, at 3:39 PM, Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(5)

Cheers

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Date: September 15, 2018 at 2:20:41 AM EDT
To: Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: Meeting with RSO

Hi George –

(b)(5)

Hope you are well!!

A 😊

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Saturday, September 15, 2018 8:20 AM

To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Heather and Ted –

(b)(5)

Thanks –

Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)

Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 6:58 PM

To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Please let me know if you need anything!

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 3:07 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thanks, Amy!

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Enjoy your evening,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 2:09 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Meeting with RSO

Hi All -

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 8:02 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks, Ted

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 1:00 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tjw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Ted,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:58 AM

To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

I will ask Keith Eichenholz.

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:50 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Eva (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

I thank you.

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:35 AM
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Eva

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:33 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

(b)(5)

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
Phone: 404-639-6439
E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:29 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Thank you!

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:23 AM
To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hello –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 5:19 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)

<fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Amy,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Take care,

Eva

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 11:12 AM

To: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Meeting with RSO

Hi Eva –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks –
Amy

From: Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 4:39 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Meeting with RSO
Importance: High

Hi Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks,

Eva

*Eva M. Holland
Senior Attorney
HHS Office of the General Counsel
Public Health Division
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., MS D-53
Atlanta, GA 30333
(404) 639-7445 (phone)
(404) 639-7351 (fax)*

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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 14:10:05 -0400
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC); Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Memo/query
Attachments: (b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted, thanks. See edits please.

Todd

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 8:04 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Is this better? Thanks for your patience as we try to get this right. Please feel free to edit that paragraph as needed.

Ted

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:02 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 7:59 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Memo/query

Hi All -

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 17, 2018, at 7:52 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

As always, thanks for all of your time, Ted

Shaunette- Amy and Todd are our SA country director and deputy.

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 15:36:19 -0400
To: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD); Gipson, Anthony (CDC/OCOO/HRO); Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:53 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Gipson, Anthony (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <osg7@cdc.gov>; Holland, Eva M. (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <btq9@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Keith

Keith A. Eichenholz
Assistant Regional Counsel
Office of the General Counsel, DHHS Region IV
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., Bldg. 21, Mailstop D-53 Atlanta, GA 30329-4027
Telephone: (404) 639-3827
Facsimile: (404) 639-7351

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From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:49 PM
To: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Gipson, Anthony (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <osg7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks, Ted

From: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:15 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Have the most recent versions gone to HRO/WRO? I edited a version they sent to me. (b)(5)
(b)(5) am not seeing Anthony on these messages.

Keith A. Eichenholz
Assistant Regional Counsel
Office of the General Counsel, DHHS Region IV
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., Bldg. 21, Mailstop D-53 Atlanta, GA 30329-4027
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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:10 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Ted, thanks. See edits please.

Todd

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 8:04 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Is this better? Thanks for your patience as we try to get this right. Please feel free to edit that paragraph as needed.

Ted

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:02 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 7:59 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Memo/query

Hi All -

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks -

Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 17, 2018, at 7:52 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2); (b)(5)

As always, thanks for all of your time, Ted

Shaunette- Amy and Todd are our SA country director and deputy.

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 14:34:53 -0400
To: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD)
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

From: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:15 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Keith A. Eichenholz
Assistant Regional Counsel
Office of the General Counsel, DHHS Region IV
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., Bldg. 21, Mailstop D-53 Atlanta, GA 30329-4027
Telephone: (404) 639-3827
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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:10 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Ted, thanks. See edits please.

Todd

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 8:04 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Is this better? Thanks for your patience as we try to get this right. Please feel free to edit that paragraph as needed.

Ted

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:02 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 7:59 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Memo/query

Hi All -

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 17, 2018, at 7:52 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

As always, thanks for all of your time, Ted

Shaunette- Amy and Todd are our SA country director and deputy.

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 14:48:48 -0400
To: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD); Gipson, Anthony (CDC/OCOO/HRO)
Subject: RE: Memo/query
Attachments: (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks, Ted

From: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:15 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <sxc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Keith A. Eichenholz
Assistant Regional Counsel
Office of the General Counsel, DHHS Region IV
1600 Clifton Road, N.E., Bldg. 21, Mailstop D-53 Atlanta, GA 30329-4027
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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:10 PM

To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <svc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Ted, thanks. See edits please.

Todd

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 8:04 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <svc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

Is this better? Thanks for your patience as we try to get this right. Please feel free to edit that paragraph as needed.

Ted

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 2:02 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <svc3@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Memo/query

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 7:59 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Eichenholz, Keith (CDC/OCOO/OGC) <yyv0@cdc.gov>; Crawford, Shaunette (CDC/OCOO/OD) <svc3@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Memo/query

Hi All -

Three quick updates:

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 17, 2018, at 7:52 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2); (b)(5)

As always, thanks for all of your time, Ted

Shaunette- Amy and Todd are our SA country director and deputy.

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 19:53:18 +0000
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Re: note to team on handover to Alfred
Attachments: image001.jpg

Hi Todd -

(b)(6) please send from you. Thanks!

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 13, 2018, at 8:33 PM, Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Amy – draft note to send to at least DCM, Iva, and Matt. Or I can if you want. T

Dear all –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

<image001.jpg>

Todd Wilson, MS

Deputy Country Director

U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

Pretoria, South Africa

Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9005

Cell: +27-82-524-4455

e-mail: twilson@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wed, 19 Sep 2018 13:15:38 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 10:11 AM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Ted –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Open to any and all other suggestions.

Best –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 4:04 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks Amy. (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 9:54 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Best –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 3:05 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Ok- (b)(2); (b)(5)

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 3:02 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Ted –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thank you for moving so swiftly on this –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, September 18, 2018 11:10 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD) <rtm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hig7@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Ted

Ted Pistorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

From: Singletary, Thelma (Lynn) (CDC/OCOO/HRO)
Sent: Mon, 24 Sep 2018 08:15:56 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hello and thank you Amy for the requested document. Continue to have a great day/week.

Respectfully,
Lynn

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 20, 2018 5:45 PM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD) <rtm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjb7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Heather, Ted, and All –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Please let me know if you have any questions.

Thank you, again, for your assistance.

With best regards –
Amy

Amy Herman-Roloff, PhD, MPH
Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext.9055
Cell: +27-82-524-0888
e-mail: bjy2@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

This e-mail is **Official - SBU**. This e-mail is **UNCLASSIFIED**.

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, September 18, 2018 11:10 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD) <rjm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Ted

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)

404-579-1250 (mobile)

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Thu, 20 Sep 2018 14:50:18 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: Re: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Thank you Amy. I know this hasn't been easy, and we all appreciate everything you've done.

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 20, 2018, at 2:26 PM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks for all of your assistance!
Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 20, 2018, at 8:06 PM, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hello all- any updates?
Thanks, Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 10:11 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Ted –

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Open to any and all other suggestions.

Best –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 4:04 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks Amy (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 9:54 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Best –

Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)

Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 3:05 PM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>

Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Ok (b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 3:02 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Ted –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thank you for moving so swiftly on this –

Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)

Sent: Tuesday, September 18, 2018 11:10 PM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD) <rjm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>

Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you both for your patience and support as this moved forward. I know this has been a trying time and I appreciate your engagement and rapid response to the swirl of inquiries that were required to generate this action. Please don't hesitate to reach out if you have any questions,

Ted

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wed, 19 Sep 2018 10:39:31 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Sorry, was on a call.

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 10:11 AM
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Ted –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Open to any and all other suggestions.

Best –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 4:04 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks Amy. (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 9:54 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi –

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Best –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wednesday, September 19, 2018 3:05 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Ok (b)(2), (b)(5)

Ted

Sent from my phone.

On Sep 19, 2018, at 3:02 AM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hi Ted –

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you for moving so swiftly on this –
Amy

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, September 18, 2018 11:10 PM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca

(CDC/CGH/OD) <rtm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>

Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Ted

Ted Pestorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 20 Sep 2018 21:45:03 +0000
To: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD); Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD); Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD); Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)
Attachments: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Heather, Ted, and All –

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Please let me know if you have any questions.

Thank you, again, for your assistance.

With best regards –
Amy

Amy Herman-Roloff, PhD, MPH
Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext.9055
Cell: +27-82-524-0888
e-mail: hjr2@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

This e-mail is **Official - SBU**. This e-mail is **UNCLASSIFIED**.

From: Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, September 18, 2018 11:10 PM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Cc: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>; Lawton, Kay E. (CDC/CGH/OD) <kel1@cdc.gov>; Wright-Fofanah, Sandra J. (CDC/CGH/OD) <sjw3@cdc.gov>; Martin, Rebecca (CDC/CGH/OD) <rtm4@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjj7@cdc.gov>

Subject: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Ted

Ted Pectorius
Dep. Dir. Mgmt & Overseas Ops
CGH/CDC

404-639-0216 (office)
404-579-1250 (mobile)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 20 Sep 2018 06:52:58 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)
Attachments:

Hi Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Regards,

Martin Steyn, MCom
Associate Director for Operations
Insights® Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000
Cell: +27-82-524-4792
E-mail: vfz3@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica>

This e-mail is **SBU** and may contain **PII**. This e-mail is **UNCLASSIFIED**.

The information contained in this e-mail is intended only for the individual/s named. If you are not the named addressee you should not disseminate, distribute or copy this e-mail. Please notify the sender immediately by e-mail if you have received this e-mail by mistake and delete this e-mail from your system. E-mail transmission cannot be guaranteed to be secure or error-free as information could be intercepted, corrupted, lost, destroyed, arrive late or incomplete, or contain viruses. The sender therefore does not accept liability for any errors or omissions in the contents of this message, which arise as a result of e-mail transmission.

(b)(2) , (b)(5) , (b)(6)

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 1 Oct 2018 06:35:23 -0400
To: Alfred Bere
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Packing out your household effects

Hi Alfred, thanks, will be in touch soon.

Todd

From: Alfred Bere (b)(6)
Sent: Monday, October 1, 2018 12:22 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re: Packing out your household effects

Dear Todd,

Thank you for the email. Regarding the shipment of household goods, the only items that I would like shipped to the US (b)(6)

The rest of the items including car, I will be keeping here in SA.

Am happy to assist with the packing process.

Regards,
Alfred

On Thu, Sep 27, 2018, 6:33 PM Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov> wrote:
Hi Alfred,

I want to let you know about the process for moving out your household items and your entitlements. I understand Martin gave you the disk for your car today, so that is complete.

For CDC, you are entitled to ship your household effects and vehicle back to your home of record in (b)(6) CDC will organize a mover to come pack and ship your items. This process may take a couple weeks to organize, with active participation on your part to ensure the move is successful. You also are entitled to ticket back to the US, same home of record, for yourself as relocation. You have up to one year from September 29, 2018 to take advantage of this entitlement, after which it will no longer be available to you. If you use the ticket and are detained for any reason, please know the USG has fulfilled its obligation and cannot issue another.

From: Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 14 Sep 2018 10:59:38 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Good morning and happy Friday.
This has been completed.

Thx
Chris

From: Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 10:55 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Good morning and happy Friday.
Will do.
Thanks
Chris

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 10:32 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>; Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Christopher, please see below for urgent action please.

Thanks,

Todd

Todd Wilson, MS
Deputy Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9005
Cell: +27-82-524-4455
e-mail: twilson@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 4:22 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>; Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 9:42 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks again - Todd

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:11 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Additional guidance will be coming from OCISO in the near future. For now, please let us know if you have any further questions.

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

-----Original Message-----

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 5:49 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan-

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Please advise

Thx Todd

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:33 PM

To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>
Subject: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hello Nathan -

I hope that this email finds you well.

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Many thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 13:48:22 -0400
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Thanks Nathan we will implement.

T

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Monday, September 17, 2018 4:28 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
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Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 9:42 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5)

Hi Nathan,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks again - Todd

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)

Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:11 PM

To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

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From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

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To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan-

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Please advise

Thx Todd

-----Original Message-----

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Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:33 PM

To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>

Subject: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hello Nathan -

I hope that this email finds you well.

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Many thanks -

Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO)
Sent: Fri, 14 Sep 2018 12:10:03 +0000
To: Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO); Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5)
Attachments: (b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Jim Wilson

CDC ITA – Southern Africa

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

OFFICE VoIP: +1 404 553 8887 | Cell: +27 (0)82 524 3555

E-mail: jwilson3@cdc.gov

From: Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:47 PM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Cheri Gatland-Lightner

From: "Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)" <ent1@cdc.gov>
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 7:11 AM
To: "Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <tiw6@cdc.gov>
CC: "Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO)" <hip5@cdc.gov>,"Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)" <bjy2@cdc.gov>,"Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)" <clg5@cdc.gov>,"Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)" <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Additional guidance will be coming from OCISO in the near future. For now, please let us know if you have any further questions.

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

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Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 5:49 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan-

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Please advise

Thx Todd

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:33 PM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>
Subject: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hello Nathan -

I hope that this email finds you well.

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Many thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

PERSONAL CUSTODY PROPERTY RECORD/HAND RECEIPT

PROPERTY ISSUED TO:	OPDIV/STAFFDIV	DIVISION/BRANCH	LOCATION: RM./BLDG.
NAME: (LAST) Bere (FIRST) Alfred (MI)		CDC/Prevention	Ubunye Building

Statement of Responsibility

I have received the item(s) listed below on the date indicated. I accept personal responsibility for the property and will surrender it upon demand, transfer, or separation from the Government. I further understand that failure on my part to exercise responsibility for the care and protection of the item(s) listed below could result in pecuniary liability established in accordance with HHS Logistics Management Manual § 101-27.5210-2.

DESCRIPTION--INCLUDING MAKE, MODEL, SERIAL NUMBER AND ACCESSORIES Laptop device, Laptop charger and Laptop bag Make: Dell Model: 7250 Service Tag (b)(6) Barcode (b)(6)	Bere Alfred (012) 424-9071			
	NAME OF PERSON RECEIVING PROPERTY	TELEPHONE NUMBER		
	SIGNATURE (b)(6)	DATE 07/05/2017		
	RETURNED	DATE		
	RECEIVED-SIGNATURE OF CUSTODIAL OFFICER			
	ITEMS ARE TO BE RETURNED TO: CDC/IT Ubunye Building (012) 424-9000			
NAME OF ISSUING PROPERTY REPRESENTATIVE	SIGNATURE	ISSUING OFFICE	LOCATION	TELEPHONE NUMBER

PERSONAL CUSTODY PROPERTY RECORD/HAND RECEIPT

PROPERTY ISSUED TO:	OPDIV/STAFFDIV	DIVISION/BRANCH	LOCATION: RM./BLDG.
NAME: (LAST) (FIRST) (MI)			

Statement of Responsibility

I have received the item(s) listed below on the date indicated. I accept personal responsibility for the property and will surrender it upon demand, transfer, or separation from the Government. I further understand that failure on my part to exercise responsibility for the care and protection of the item(s) listed below could result in pecuniary liability established in accordance with HHS Logistics Management Manual § 101-27.5210-2.

DESCRIPTION--INCLUDING MAKE, MODEL, SERIAL NUMBER AND ACCESSORIES				
	NAME OF PERSON RECEIVING PROPERTY	TELEPHONE NUMBER		
	SIGNATURE	DATE		
	RETURNED	DATE		
	RECEIVED-SIGNATURE OF CUSTODIAL OFFICER			
	ITEMS ARE TO BE RETURNED TO:			
NAME OF ISSUING PROPERTY REPRESENTATIVE	SIGNATURE	ISSUING OFFICE	LOCATION	TELEPHONE NUMBER

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Mon, 17 Sep 2018 10:28:17 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA
Attachments: Chain of Custody Form_04-09-15.docx

Todd,

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 9:42 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan,

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Thanks again - Todd

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:11 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R.

(CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

-----Original Message-----

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 5:49 AM

To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan-

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Please advise

Thx Todd

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From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:33 PM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>
Subject: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hello Nathan -

I hope that this email finds you well.

(b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Many thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

SENSITIVE

BUT

UNCLASSIFIED

(SBU) INFORMATION

This document contains information that may be exempt from public release under the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) (5 U.S.C. 552). Exemption 2 applies. Approval by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention Document Control Officer, Office of Security and Emergency Preparedness, and the CDC FOIA Officer, prior to public release via the FOIA Office is required.

SENSITIVE

BUT

UNCLASSIFIED

(SBU) INFORMATION

This document contains information that may be exempt from public release under the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) (5 U.S.C. 552). Exemption 2 applies. Approval by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention Document Control Officer, Office of Security and Emergency Preparedness, and the CDC FOIA Officer, prior to public release via the FOIA Office is required.

From: Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)
Sent: Fri, 14 Sep 2018 10:38:53 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO); Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 10:36 AM
To: Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>; Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

(b)(2), (b)(5)

T

From: Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 4:34 PM
To: Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>; Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 10:27 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

(b)(2), (b)(5)

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 10:22 AM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>; Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 9:42 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Thanks again - Todd

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:11 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

-----Original Message-----

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 5:49 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan-

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Please advise

Thx Todd

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:33 PM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>

Subject: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hello Nathan -

I hope that this email finds you well.

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Many thanks -
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 08:45:42 +0000
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Items to address urgently

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Jim

Jim Wilson

CDC/OCIO/ITSO ITA – Southern Africa

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

OFFICE VoIP: +1 404 553 8887 | Cell: +27 (0)82 524 3555

E-mail: jwilson3@cdc.gov

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 7:30 AM
To: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: Items to address urgently

(b)(2), (b)(5)

T

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 12, 2018 9:05 PM
To: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vfz3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>
Subject: Items to address urgently

Hi Martin, per our call please:

(b)(2), (b)(5)

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thx Todd

Todd Wilson, MS
Deputy Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9005
Cell: +27-82-524-4455
e-mail: twilson@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Wed, 3 Oct 2018 06:36:49 -0400
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 8:16 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Best,

Todd

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Tuesday, October 2, 2018 1:31 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

Sorry about not checking in on this earlier. I've been on TDY and offline.

I just wanted to ensure that you didn't have any outstanding questions on this issue. (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Happy to assist however I can.

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 9:42 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5)

Hi Nathan,

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Thanks again - Todd

From: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 1:11 PM
To: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Gatland-Lightner, Cheri (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <clg5@cdc.gov>; Tanner, Allison R. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/OCISO) <aid2@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Todd,

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Nathan Volk, MS, CISSP
Information Systems Security Officer (ISSO)
Informatics and Information Resources Office
Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Email: nvolk@cdc.gov
(land) 404-718-4797

-----Original Message-----

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 14, 2018 5:49 AM
To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hi Nathan-

(b)(2); (b)(5)

Please advise

Thx Todd

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:33 PM

To: Volk, Nathan (CDC/CGH/OD) <ent1@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Wilson, James W. (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/ITSO) <hip5@cdc.gov>

Subject: Personnel issue - CDC SA

Hello Nathan -

I hope that this email finds you well.

I am writing to request your guidance and assistance with a personnel issue we are having in CDC South Africa.

(b)(2), (b)(5)

Many thanks -

Amy

Sent from my iPhone

From: Glenshaw, Mary T. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 10 Sep 2018 08:49:22 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Hi Peter and colleagues

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Thanks

Mary

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Sunday, September 9, 2018 4:35 PM

To: Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna

(CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wxk7@cdc.gov>; Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Glenshaw, Mary T. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fev5@cdc.gov>

Subject: Re: SACTWU summary

Hi All -

(b)(5)

(b)(5)

Thanks!
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

> On Sep 7, 2018, at 5:51 PM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:

>

> HI All –

>

> Thank you for your work on this and for the short turn-around.

>

> Thank you all for getting updates to Jonas and to Jonas for compiling this!

>

(b)(5)

>

> Todd, please do one final review once Michelle and Peter update.

>

> Thanks –

> Amy

>

> From: Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> Sent: Friday, September 7, 2018 9:40 AM

> To: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy

> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)

> <pbv7@cdc.gov>

> Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa

> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wxk7@cdc.gov>;

> Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle

> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>

> Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

>

> Dear Jonas,

>

> Many thanks. Please see my comments in track changes. M

>

> [Michelle Smith2]

>

> From: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> Sent: Friday, September 7, 2018 3:18 AM

> To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> <bjy2@cdc.gov<<mailto:bjy2@cdc.gov>>>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov<<mailto:pbv7@cdc.gov>>>; Smith, Michelle

> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov<<mailto:uwt7@cdc.gov>>>

> Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov<<mailto:tiw6@cdc.gov>>>;

> Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> <vka5@cdc.gov<<mailto:vka5@cdc.gov>>>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

> <pen5@cdc.gov<mailto:pen5@cdc.gov>>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <wjk7@cdc.gov<mailto:wjk7@cdc.gov>>
> Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
>
> Hello Amy,
> Attached is a first draft of the requested summary. Please have a look and let me know what you think.
>
> Thanks,
> Jonas
>
> From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> Sent: Wednesday, September 5, 2018 10:00 AM
> To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
> <pbv7@cdc.gov<mailto:pbv7@cdc.gov>>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <yxj7@cdc.gov<mailto:yxj7@cdc.gov>>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <uwt7@cdc.gov<mailto:uwt7@cdc.gov>>
> Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov<mailto:tiw6@cdc.gov>>;
> Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <vka5@cdc.gov<mailto:vka5@cdc.gov>>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <pen5@cdc.gov<mailto:pen5@cdc.gov>>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <wjk7@cdc.gov<mailto:wjk7@cdc.gov>>
> Subject: SACTWU summary
> Importance: High
>
> Hi Team –

(b)(5)

>
> Contents are:

(b)(5)

>

> Best regards –

> Amy

> (b)(5)

>

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Fri, 7 Sep 2018 15:51:23 +0000
To: Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
Attachments: (b)(5)
Summary.docx

HI All –

Thank you for your work on this and for the short turn-around.

Thank you all for getting updates to Jonas and to Jonas for compiling this!

(b)(5)

Todd, please do one final review once Michelle and Peter update.

Thanks –
Amy

From: Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 7, 2018 9:40 AM
To: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <>wxk7@cdc.gov>; Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Dear Jonas,

Many thanks. Please see my comments in track changes. M

Michelle Smith

Extramural Resource Specialist,
Extramural Branch
Division of Global HIV/AIDS
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9022
Cell: +27-82-524-4417
e-mail: uwt7@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Friday, September 7, 2018 3:18 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wvk7@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Hello Amy,
Attached is a first draft of the requested summary. Please have a look and let me know what you think.

Thanks,
Jonas

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 5, 2018 10:00 AM
To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxi7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wvk7@cdc.gov>
Subject: SACTWU summary
Importance: High

Hi Team –

(b)(5)

I've asked Jonas to coordinate the collection of the elements and finalize the draft (thank you Jonas for being extra hands for us right now!). **Michelle and Peter – please send your elements to Jonas by COB tomorrow (Thursday).**

Best regards –
Amy

From: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
Sent: Thu, 13 Sep 2018 05:12:47 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Glenshaw, Mary T. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
Attachments: Geographical Coverage SACTWU FY15-FY18.xls

Also sending the final coverage and achievement data for SACTWU.

Still not too clear on how to triangulate that with other data though. Will talk to Patrick about it.

Peter

Peter Vranken
Senior Program Officer
MassGenics Inc, assigned to:
Global AIDS Program - South Africa
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
PO box 9536, Brooklyn 0001
Pretoria, South Africa
Cell. +27 82 5243888
Tel. +27 12 4249000
Fax. +27 12 3464286
pbv7@cdc.gov

-----Original Message-----

From: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
Sent: Thursday, September 13, 2018 10:10 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wxk7@cdc.gov>; Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Glenshaw, Mary T. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fev5@cdc.gov>
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Re-sending with final SACTWU achievement under THC included.

Peter

Peter Vranken
Senior Program Officer
MassGenics Inc, assigned to:
Global AIDS Program - South Africa
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention PO box 9536, Brooklyn 0001 Pretoria, South Africa Cell. +27 82 5243888 Tel. +27 12 4249000 Fax. +27 12 3464286 pbv7@cdc.gov

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Monday, September 10, 2018 10:26 PM

To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wxk7@cdc.gov>; Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Glenshaw, Mary T. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fev5@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Thanks all -

Over to Todd for final review once all of the pieces are in.

Patrick - any additional ideas re. how to validate 2016 MER data?

Thanks -

Amy

-----Original Message-----

From: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)

Sent: Monday, September 10, 2018 3:21 PM

To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>

Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <vka5@cdc.gov>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wxk7@cdc.gov>; Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Glenshaw, Mary T. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fev5@cdc.gov>

Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Here's the latest version of the summary document as it stands. I've made my inputs on top of Michelle's. Still a few data (from THC, go figure!) I'm still waiting for.

Geographical coverage of SACTWU activities over last few years also forthcoming.

Peter

Peter Vranken

Senior Program Officer

MassGenics Inc, assigned to:

Global AIDS Program - South Africa

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention PO box 9536, Brooklyn 0001 Pretoria, South Africa Cell. +27 82

5243888 Tel. +27 12 4249000 Fax. +27 12 3464286 pbv7@cdc.gov

-----Original Message-----

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Sunday, September 09, 2018 4:35 PM

To: Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>

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Subject: Re: SACTWU summary

Hi All -

(b)(5)

Peter - could you please send a list of geography by year where SACTWU has been working for 2016, 2017, and 2018?

+ Mary to see if she knows of any other surveys that may provide additional data points.

Thanks!
Amy

Sent from my iPhone

> On Sep 7, 2018, at 5:51 PM, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov> wrote:
>
> HI All –
>
> Thank you for your work on this and for the short turn-around.
>
> Thank you all for getting updates to Jonas and to Jonas for compiling this!
>
> I've reviewed and have some questions for Michelle and Peter (Michelle I've attached the forensic audit report from Mazars). Please prioritize this first thing on Monday AM.
>
> Todd, please do one final review once Michelle and Peter update.
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> Thanks –
> Amy
>
> From: Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> Sent: Friday, September 7, 2018 9:40 AM
> To: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy
> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
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> Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Briggs-Hagen, Melissa
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> <pen5@cdc.gov>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <wxk7@cdc.gov>;
> Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hff4@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle
> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
> Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
>
> Dear Jonas,
>
> Many thanks. Please see my comments in track changes. M
>
> [Michelle Smith2]
>
> From: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> Sent: Friday, September 7, 2018 3:18 AM
> To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <bjy2@cdc.gov<mailto:bjy2@cdc.gov>>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov<mailto:pbv7@cdc.gov>>; Smith, Michelle

> (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov<mailto:uwt7@cdc.gov>>
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> <pen5@cdc.gov<mailto:pen5@cdc.gov>>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <wxk7@cdc.gov<mailto:wxk7@cdc.gov>>
> Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
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> Hello Amy,
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> Thanks,
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> Sent: Wednesday, September 5, 2018 10:00 AM
> To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
> <pbv7@cdc.gov<mailto:pbv7@cdc.gov>>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <yxj7@cdc.gov<mailto:yxj7@cdc.gov>>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
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> <wxk7@cdc.gov<mailto:wxk7@cdc.gov>>
> Subject: SACTWU summary
> Importance: High
>
> Hi Team –
>
> I would like us to draft a 1-2 page summary of CDC’s funding to SACTWU and partner management. This is a document that can be shared with NDOH, OGAC, DGHT leadership, etc. that summarizes our award and proactive management of our prime partners and their program.
>
> Contents are:
>
> · Award history (Michelle):
>
> o SACTWU prime
>
> o SACTWU sub w/ THCA
>
> o SACTWU sub w/Aurum
>
> · HQ TDY Summary – Findings and remedial actions (Jonas)
>
> · Aurum sub to SACTWU – quality (program and data) monitoring and summary (Peter)
>
> I’ve asked Jonas to coordinate the collection of the elements and finalize the draft (thank you Jonas for being extra hands for us right now!). Michelle and Peter – please send your elements to Jonas by COB tomorrow (Thursday).
>
> Best regards –
> Amy
> <00 TBHIV Care SACTWU Forensic Audit Preliminary Report 051017.pdf>
> <image001.jpg> <SWHP Summary.docx>

Province	District	Y15/1+2	Y15/3	Y15/4	Y16/1	Y16/2	Y16/3	Y16/4	Y17/1	Y17/2	Y17/3	Y17/4	Y18/1	Y18/2	Y18/3	Y18/4
	fs Thabo Mofutsanyane District Municipality	4,405	1,358	2,361	2,994	2,176	1,539	3,159	1,129	496	1,983	9,770				
	fs Xhariep District Municipality	430	426	110	311	203	25	12								
	gp City of Tshwane Metropolitan Municipality	4,311	1,308	2,962	2,573	353	493	1,369	136							
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz Amajuba District Municipality	2,665	1,471	2,155	1,263	355	1,263	1,387								
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz eThekweni Metropolitan Municipality	5,146	1,870	2,664	2,389	1,045	1,931	2,260	2,160	2,794	7,826	9,684	3,115	1,826	2,442	424
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz iLembe District Municipality	4,311	2,415	2,400	1,965	750	1,091	1,075								
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz King Cetshwayo District Municipality	6,374	2,583	3,660	3,203	1,781	2,033	2,259	1,863	1,528	3,573	5,293	3,282	3,405	2,843	630
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz Ugu District Municipality	3,019	2,110	2,499	1,880	741	1,460	1,262	627	874	1,064	2,050	939	1,957	1,277	258
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz uMgungundlovu District Municipality	310	258	554	207	206	756	1,125	1,071	3,267	3,835	5,529	504	1,587	940	84
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz Umkhanyakude District Municipality	3,033	1,006	1,799	1,834	840	1,124	967	1,223	1,378	3,192	5,873	1,715	543		
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz Umzinyathi District Municipality	3,905	2,085	2,397	1,541	948	1,473	2,581								
kz KwaZulu-Natal Province	kz Uthukela District Municipality	4,162	2,020	2,692	2,272	1,118	2,117	3,587	2,257	2,228	3,644	6,994	3,707	2,779	2,852	7
lp Limpopo Province	lp Sekhukhune District Municipality	1,396	406	1,243	1,106	142										
mp Mpumalanga Province	mp Gert Sibande District Municipality	574	343	356	251	192	1,051	186			130	260				
nc Northern Cape Province	nc Frances Baard District Municipality	3,693	1,138	1,831	2,699	845	238	1,293								
wc Western Cape Province	wc Cape Winelands District Municipality	1,618	689	772	853	651	585	148					60			
wc Western Cape Province	wc City of Cape Town Metropolitan Municipality	1,329	421	699	516	520	547	834	1,068	974	1,145	2,015	895	713	941	311
wc Western Cape Province	wc Eden District Municipality	982	598	474	774	476	381									
	Total	51,663	22,505	31,648	28,631	13,342	18,107	23,504	11,534	13,539	26,392	47,468	14,217	12,810	11,295	1,714

From: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
Sent: Fri, 7 Sep 2018 02:07:38 -0400
To: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
Attachments: SWHP Note - VMMC in COP17.docx

Hi all,

Attached is a (detailed) summary statement from Aurum (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Peter

Peter Vranken

Senior Program Officer
MassGenics Inc, assigned to:
Global AIDS Program - South Africa
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
PO box 9536, Brooklyn 0001
Pretoria, South Africa
Cell. +27 82 5243888
Tel. +27 12 4249000
Fax. +27 12 3464286
pbv7@cdc.gov

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Sent: Friday, September 07, 2018 3:18 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
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Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

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Thanks,
Jonas

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To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>

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Subject: SACTWU summary

Importance: High

Hi Team –

(b)(5)

Best regards –
Amy

From: Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 6 Sep 2018 10:30:28 -0400
To: Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR); Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
Attachments: SACTWU-CoAg Mgmt.docx

Hey Jonas,
Michelle and I put this together (b)(5)
(b)(5) so you can take what you want for the final version.
Let us know if you have any questions.
Kathryn

From: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, September 6, 2018 7:31 AM
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
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Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

+ Kathryn who is working on parts of this as well.

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Wednesday, September 5, 2018 4:00 PM
To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR) <pbv7@cdc.gov>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <yxj7@cdc.gov>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <uwt7@cdc.gov>
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(b)(5)

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Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: SACTWU summary
Attachments: SWHP Note - VMMC in COP17.docx, SACTWU Site Visit Report_04.22.2016.docx, SWHP Summary_MS Edits.docx

Dear Amy,

+ Katie

Please see my comments and other attached supporting documentation.

Sincerely,

Michelle Smith

Extramural Resource Specialist,
Extramural Branch
Division of Global HIV/AIDS
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9022
Cell: +27-82-524-4417
e-mail: uwt7@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

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Subject: RE: SACTWU summary

Dear Jonas,

Many thanks. Please see my comments in track changes. M

Michelle Smith

Extramural Resource Specialist,
Extramural Branch
Division of Global HIV/AIDS
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext. 9022
Cell: +27-82-524-4417
e-mail: uwt7@cdc.gov

Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

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Subject: SACTWU summary

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Cc: Brown, Kathryn F. (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Sobush, Kathleen (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
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(b)(5)

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Subject: Re: SACTWU summary

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(b)(5)

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> Sent: Wednesday, September 5, 2018 10:00 AM
> To: Vranken, Peter (CDC/CGH/DGHT) (CTR)
> <pbv7@cdc.gov<mailto:pbv7@cdc.gov>>; Hines, Jonas (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <yxj7@cdc.gov<mailto:yxj7@cdc.gov>>; Smith, Michelle (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <uwt7@cdc.gov<mailto:uwt7@cdc.gov>>
> Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov<mailto:tiw6@cdc.gov>>;
> Briggs-Hagen, Melissa (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <vka5@cdc.gov<mailto:vka5@cdc.gov>>; Nadol, Patrick (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <pen5@cdc.gov<mailto:pen5@cdc.gov>>; Taback-Esra, Rayna (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
> <wxk7@cdc.gov<mailto:wxk7@cdc.gov>>
> Subject: SACTWU summary
> Importance: High

>
> Hi Team –

>
> (b)(5)

>
> I've asked Jonas to coordinate the collection of the elements and finalize the draft (thank you Jonas for being extra hands for us right now!). Michelle and Peter – please send your elements to Jonas by COB tomorrow (Thursday).

>
> Best regards –

> Amy

> <00 TBHIV Care SACTWU Forensic Audit Preliminary Report 051017.pdf>

> <image001.jpg> <SWHP Summary.docx>

From: Knight, Nancy (CDC/CGH/DGHP)
Sent: Tue, 4 Sep 2018 17:41:15 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: RE: Staff Communication Regarding Alfred Bere

Amy,

I'm just back from (b)(6)
(b)(6) (b)(5)
(b)(5)

(b)(5) Thinking of you and the
whole CDC SA team.
Nancy

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thursday, August 30, 2018 10:03 AM
To: Knight, Nancy (CDC/CGH/DGHP) <fma2@cdc.gov>
Subject: FW: Staff Communication Regarding Alfred Bere

Hi Nancy –

I hope you are well.

(b)(5)

Happy to chat –
A

From: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, August 27, 2018 10:19 AM
To: CDC CGH DGHT SoAf DGHT ALL <SADGHAALL@cdc.gov>
Subject: Staff Communication Regarding Alfred Bere

Good Morning CDC South Africa Family -

Dr. Alfred Bere, USDH CDC South Africa Prevention Branch Chief, was arrested on August 25, 2018 in Musina. The arrest warrant lists the charges as "Fraud and Corruption". We understand that the charges against Alfred may be related to an ongoing HAWKS investigation of The South African Clothing and Textiles Workers Union (SACTWU), which is a male circumcision sub-partner to CDC's prime partner TB HIV Care Association.

(b)(5)

What's next?

- If you are approached by the media, standard media protocol applies, so please refer them to Chantelle (xyg8@cdc.gov).
- If you are approached by a partner or stakeholder, please refer them to either myself (bjy2@cdc.gov) or the Deputy Country Director, Todd Wilson (tiw6@cdc.gov).
- We will continue to keep you updated as more facts emerge. (b)(5)

(b)(5)

Regards,
Amy

Amy Herman-Roloff, PhD, MPH
Country Director
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000 ext.9055
Cell: +27-82-524-0888
e-mail: bjy2@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica/>

From: Collins, Matilda (CDC/OCOO/HRO)
Sent: Tue, 4 Sep 2018 15:48:28 -0400
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Acosta, Herman (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/MISO) (CTR); Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Edwards, Kamilia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD); eva
Subject: RE: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Respectfully,

Matilda Y. Collins

Human Resources Specialist (ER/LR)
Center for Disease Control & Prevention (CDC)
Human Resources Office (HRO)
Workforce Relations Division (WRO)
4770 Buford Hwy
Mail Stop K-73, Atlanta, GA 30341
Office: 770-488-1290 / BB: 404-993-3633 / Fax: 770-471-8882
vjq3@cdc.gov

Your feedback is important to us. Please take a few moments to complete a brief survey on the service provided to you.

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From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Tuesday, September 4, 2018 3:31 PM
To: Collins, Matilda (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <vjq3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Acosta, Herman (CDC/OCOO/OCIO/MISO) (CTR) <kof2@cdc.gov>; Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjj7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>; Parker,

Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>; Edwards, Kamilia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fja3@cdc.gov>; Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <exu4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>; eva <holland@cdc.gov>

Subject: Re: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hi Matilda, (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

-Heather

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 4, 2018, at 3:17 PM, Collins, Matilda (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <vjq3@cdc.gov> wrote:

Hello Heather,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Respectfully,

Matilda Y. Collins

Human Resources Specialist (ER/LR)

Center for Disease Control & Prevention (CDC)

Human Resources Office (HRO)

Workforce Relations Division (WRO)

4770 Buford Hwy

Mail Stop K-73, Atlanta, GA 30341

Office: 770-488-1290 / BB: 404-993-3633 / Fax: 770-471-8882

vjq3@cdc.gov

Your feedback is important to us. Please take a few moments to complete a brief survey on the service provided to you.

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From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)

Sent: Monday, September 3, 2018 9:23 AM

To: Collins, Matilda (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <viq3@cdc.gov>

Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gp4@cdc.gov>; Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>; Edwards, Kamalia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fja3@cdc.gov>; Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <exu4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>

Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Hello Matilda,

I hope you are having an enjoyable holiday weekend!

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you for your help,

Heather

Heather B. Pumphrey, MA

Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)

Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health

Centers for Disease Control & Prevention

Phone: 404-639-6439

E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Mon, 3 Sep 2018 13:58:27 -0400
To: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Edwards, Kamilia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT); Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD)
Subject: Re (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Good afternoon and happy Monday.

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thx
Chris

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hbp7@cdc.gov>
Date: September 3, 2018 at 1:29:03 PM EDT
To: Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>
Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjb7@cdc.gov>, Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>, Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>, Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>, Edwards, Kamilia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fja3@cdc.gov>, Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <exu4@cdc.gov>, Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: Re (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you for this information Chris. (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Sent from my iPhone

On Sep 3, 2018, at 12:33 PM, Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov> wrote:

Heather,
Good afternoon and happy Monday.
Please see below.

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thanks
Chris

From: Pumphrey, Heather (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Monday, September 3, 2018 9:23 AM
To: Collins, Matilda (CDC/OCOO/HRO) <viq3@cdc.gov>
Cc: Tomlinson, Hank (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <hjg7@cdc.gov>; Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <bjy2@cdc.gov>; Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <tiw6@cdc.gov>; Bicego, George (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <gpb4@cdc.gov>; Parker, Christopher (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <csp2@cdc.gov>; Edwards, Kamilia Johnson (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <fja3@cdc.gov>; Grant-Greene, Yoran (CDC/CGH/DGHT) <exu4@cdc.gov>; Pestorius, Ted (CDC/CGH/OD) <fpp0@cdc.gov>
Subject: (b)(2); (b)(5); (b)(6)

Hello Matilda,

I hope you are having an enjoyable holiday weekend!

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Thank you for your help,

Heather
Heather B. Pumphrey, MA
Deputy Director for Global Management & Operations (Acting)
Division of Global HIV & TB, Center for Global Health
Centers for Disease Control & Prevention
Phone: 404-639-6439
E-mail: hbp7@cdc.gov

From: Steyn, Martin G. (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Sent: Thu, 20 Sep 2018 10:13:42 -0400
To: Herman-Roloff, Amy (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Cc: Wilson, Todd (CDC/CGH/DGHT)
Subject: (b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)
Attachments:

Good afternoon Amy,

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)

Regards,

Martin Steyn, MCom
Associate Director for Operations
Insights® Discovery Accredited Facilitator
Division of Global HIV/AIDS and TB
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Pretoria, South Africa
Tel: +27-12-424-9000
Cell: +27-82-524-4792
E-mail: vfz3@cdc.gov
Web: <http://www.cdc.gov/globalhealth/countries/southafrica>

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(b)(2) , (b)(5) , (b)(6)

(b)(2), (b)(5), (b)(6)